

ISSN 2181-2357

XALQARO NAZARIY VA AMALIY TADQIQOTLAR
JURNALI

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL RESEARCH

JURNAL FARG'ONA POLITEXNIKA
INSTITUTI HAMKORLIGIDA NASHR
ETILADI

VOLUME 2,
Issue 6-8
2022

«Al-Ferganus» MChJ.

A. M. Abdullayev

2-tom, 6-8 -son.

«Nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar xalqaro jurnali»

Ilmiy jurnal.

Iyun-Avgust 2022 y.

2021 yil noyabrdan beri nashr etilmoqda.

Oyiga bir marta nashr etiladi. 16+

Tahririyat kengashi raisi Salomov O'ktam Raximovich, Rector of FerPI

Bosh muharrir K. I. Kurpayanidi

Tahririyat hay'ati: A.M.Abdullaev, M.S.Ashurov, E.A.Mo'minova, K.X.Abduraxmonov, A.N.Asaul, A.V.Burkov, U.V.G'ofurov, M.A.Ikromov, D.Kudbiev, E.S.Margianiti, B.Obrenovich, L.NA Sultonov, L.NA. , A.Xasanov, Sh.T.Karimov, Sh.Sh.Salixanova, U.K.Alimov, S.M.Turabdjano, B.A.Alimatov, R.J.Tozhiyev, A.A.Risqulov, B.M.Tursunov, A.A.Shermukhamedovsh, Y.S.A. H.A.Akramov, M.X.Hakimov, Sh.M.Iskandarova, Z.M.Sobirova, A.M.Muxtorova, L.M.Babaxo'jaeva.

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<https://alferganus.uz/en/site/index>

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IF(Impact Factor) **8.7 / 2021**
<http://journalseeker.researchbib.com/view/issn/2181-2357>

TOGETHER WE REACH THE GOAL
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<http://sjifactor.com/passport.php?id=21994>

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti administratsiyasi huzuridagi axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligida ro'yxatga olingan.

Ro'yxatga olish № 1189 Berilgan sanasi: 17-06-2021.

Xalqaro nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar jurnali Crossref, OpenAIRE, Google Scholar bazalariga kiritilgan.

Impact-faktor 2021 Evaluation Pending

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Jurnal jahon va mintaqaviy darajada fan va amaliyotning rivojlanish masalalariga bag'ishlangan.

Jurnal olimlar, o'qituvchilar, doktorantlar, talabalar uchun mo'ljallangan.

Nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar xalqaro jurnali.

2022. T. 2. №6-8. <https://alferganus.uz>

ISSN 2181-2357

9 772181 235007 >

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2022 Farg'ona, O'zbekiston

«Al-Ferganus» LLC.
A. M. Abdullaev
“International journal of theoretical and practical research”
Scientific Journal.
Published since November 2021.
Schedule: monthly. 16+

Volume 2, Issue 6-8
June-August, 2022.

Chairman of the Editorial Board Salomov Uktam Rakhimovich, FarPI rektori

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Fergana city, Fergana str., 86.
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E-mail:

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IF(Impact Factor) **8.7 / 2021**

<http://journalseeker.researchbib.com/view/issn/2181-2357>

TOGETHER WE REACH THE GOAL
SJIF 2022: 5,962

<http://sjifactor.com/passport.php?id=21994>

Registered with the Agency of Information and Mass Communications under the Administration of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan.
Registration No. 1189 dated 17-06-2021.

The journal "International Journal of Theoretical and Practical Research" is included Crossref, OpenAIRE, Google Scholar.

Impact-factor 2021 Evaluation Pending

License type supported CC: Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0).

The Journal addresses issues of global and regional Science and Practice. For scientists, teachers, doctoral students, students.

(2022). International journal of theoretical and practical research, 2(6-8).

<https://alferganus.uz>

ISSN 2181-2357

9 772181 235007 >

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«Al-Ferganus» ООО.

А. М. Абдуллаев

Том 2, Номер 6-8.

«Международный журнал теоретических и практических исследований»

Научный журнал.

Июнь-Август 2022 г.

Издается с ноября 2021 г.

Выходит один раз в месяц. 16+

Председатель редакционного совета Саломов Уктам Рахимович, ректор ФерПИ

Главный редактор К. И. Курпаяниди

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Тел. +998971003888

<https://alferganus.uz/en/site/index>

E-mail: alferganus.ltd@gmail.com

IF(Impact Factor) 8.7 / 2021

[http://journalseeker.research](http://journalseeker.researchbib.com/view/issn/2181-2357)

[bib.com/view/issn/2181-](http://journalseeker.researchbib.com/view/issn/2181-2357)

[2357](http://journalseeker.researchbib.com/view/issn/2181-2357)

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[http://sjifactor.com/pass](http://sjifactor.com/passport.php?id=21994)

[port.php?id=21994](http://sjifactor.com/passport.php?id=21994)

Зарегистрирован в Агентстве информации и массовых коммуникаций при Администрации

Президента Республики Узбекистан.

Регистрации № 1189 от 17-06-2021.

Журнал «Международный журнал теоретических и практических исследований» включен в Crossref, OpenAIRE, Google Scholar.

Импакт-факторы журнала: 2021 Evaluation Pending

Тип лицензии CC поддерживаемый журналом: Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0).

В журнале рассматриваются вопросы развития мировой и региональной науки и практики. Для ученых, преподавателей, докторантов, студентов.

Международный журнал теоретических и практических исследований. 2022. Т. 2. №6-8.

<https://alferganus.uz>

ISSN 2181-2357

9 772181 235007 >

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2022, Фергана, Узбекистан

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International journal of
theoretical and practical
research

Scientific Journal

Year: 2022 Issue: 6-8 Volume: 2

Published: 31.08.2022

<http://alferganus.uz>

Citation:

Abdullaev, A.M., (2022). Innovation as a driver of modernization of economy of Uzbekistan. *SJ International journal of theoretical and practical research*, 2 (6-8),22-31.

Abdullaev, A.M., (2022). Innovation as a driver of modernization of economy of Uzbekistan. *Nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar xalqaro jurnali*, 2 (6-8), 22-31.

Doi:

<https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7188381>

QR-Article

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UDC 338.45

INNOVATION AS A DRIVER OF MODERNIZATION OF ECONOMY OF UZBEKISTAN

Abstract. *In order to ensure the competitiveness of products, modern economies of the world make a decisive bet on the transformation of scientific knowledge into a new consumer value that has qualitatively higher properties compared to analogues presented on the world market. That is why innovation is an important factor in the development of the national economy. Today, as world experience shows, there is no alternative to the innovative way of development. Creation, implementation and wide dissemination of new products, services and technological processes they become key factors of economic growth, increasing the efficiency of economic activity and competitiveness of enterprises. In the article the category of innovation. It analyzes the innovation policy in Uzbekistan in the context of globalization. On this basis, it found that innovation is a driver of economic growth in Uzbekistan.*

Key words: *globalization, the driver, the innovation, the crisis, the economy of Uzbekistan.*

ИННОВАЦИИ КАК ДРАЙВЕР МОДЕРНИЗАЦИИ ЭКОНОМИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАНА

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Аннотация. В целях обеспечения конкурентоспособности продукции современные экономики мира делают решающую ставку на трансформацию научных знаний в новую потребительскую ценность, обладающую качественно более высокими свойствами по сравнению с аналогами, представленными на мировом рынке. Именно поэтому инновации являются важным фактором в развитии национальной экономики. Сегодня, как показывает мировой опыт, альтернативы инновационному пути развития нет. Создание, внедрение и широкое распространение новых продуктов, услуг и технологических процессов становятся ключевыми факторами экономического роста, повышая эффективность хозяйственной деятельности и конкурентоспособность предприятий. В статье рассматривается категория инновации. В нем анализируется инновационная политика Узбекистана в контексте глобализации. На этой основе было выяснено, какие инновации являются движущей силой экономического роста в Узбекистане.

Ключевые слова: глобализация, драйвер, инновация, кризис, экономика Узбекистана.

ИННОВАЦИЯЛАР ЎЗБЕКИСТОН ИҚТИСОДИЁТИНИ МОДЕРНИЗАЦИЯЛАШ ОМИЛИ СИФАТИДА

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Аннотация. Маҳсулотларнинг рақобатбардошлигини таъминлаш учун дунёнинг замонавий иқтисодиёти илмий билимларни жаҳон бозорида тақдим этилган аналогларга нисбатан сифат жиҳатидан юқори хусусиятларга ега бўлган янги истеъмол қийматига айлантиришга ҳал қилувчи пул тикади. Шунинг учун инновация миллий иқтисодиётни ривожлантиришнинг муҳим омилидир. Бугунги кунда, жаҳон тажрибаси шуни кўрсатадики, ривожланишнинг инновацион усулига алтернатива йўқ. Янги маҳсулотлар, хизматлар ва технологик жараёнларни яратиш, амалга ошириш ва кенг тарқатиш иқтисодий ўсишнинг асосий омилларига айланмоқда, иқтисодий фаолият самарадорлиги ва корхоналарнинг рақобатбардошлигини оширмоқда. Мақолада инновация категорияси кўриб чиқилган. Унда глобаллашув шароитида Ўзбекистоннинг инновацион сиёсати таҳлил қилинган. Шу асосда Ўзбекистонда иқтисодий ўсишнинг ҳаракатлантирувчи кучи қайси янгиликлар эканлиги аниқланди.

Калит сўзлар: глобаллашув, ҳайдовчи, инновация, инқироз, Ўзбекистон иқтисодиёти.

Introduction

Strategy of socio-economic development of the Republic of Uzbekistan before 2030 targets increased efficiency, diversification and competitiveness of the real sector

of the economy based on the formation an innovative economy that meets the objective requirements of implementation advances in science in production, improving the quality of modern education. These goals can be achieved by reorienting the economy to an innovative way of development that allows you to form such a socio-economic environment conducive to solving scientific and technical problems and creating high-tech industries [4,8,9,11,18].

In the wave of global financial-economic crisis, the countries with transaction economy have been considering the possible consequences of financial crisis for their economies. The economic policy of the country is directed, first of all, to the searching own way of modernization of economies, considering historical course of world crisis facts, they make conclusions about possibility of achievement of any positive results only by drawing up bilateral and multipartite agreements, entering regional communities, using own approaches for transformation of national economies, liberalization of foreign economic activity, stimulate transparency of economies; by every possible ways to enhance competitiveness of production, more fully use potential capacity of the country, and on this base acceleration of creating market relations in the country, that lead to further integration to the world economic community [1,5,7,10,12].

Analysis of the literature on the topic

Over the past decades, the role of human capital, science, knowledge and highly qualified personnel among the factors of economic growth has been steadily growing in the global economy and, as a result, there is an increase in the share of high-tech, knowledge-intensive industries in the structure of industrial production. Countries are embarking on an innovative path of development, and the processes of globalization of the world economy have determined the conditions for this transition:

an innovative path of development is available for countries with macroeconomic and political stability and a developed competitive an environment with high scientific and technical potential and an effective national innovation system;

for economies with a high degree of industrialization and developed export-import relations.

The variety of theoretical and methodological problems of the study of innovative development of the economy has led to the existence at present of different points of view on this process and ambiguous approaches to the analysis of its features. As a scientific direction, innovative development has become widespread thanks to the works of such scientists as J. Schumpeter, P. Drucker, D. Clark, G. Mensch, D. Bell, E. Denisov, T. Kuhn, M. Porter and K. Arrow. The Russian scientific community of researchers of this problem is represented by the works of L.I. Abalkin, S.Y. Glazyev, A.G. Gryaznova, A.A. Dynkin, A.G. Zeldner, A.N. Illarionov, B.JI. Inozemtseva, G.B. Kleiner, V.V. Kulikova, I.N. Myslyaeva and others.

Our domestic scientists are also fruitfully engaged in the development of issues related to the peculiarities of the innovative development of the economy Gulyamov S.S., Abdullaev A.M. They paid special attention to the managerial aspects and methods of state regulation of the innovative potential of the Republic of Uzbekistan. They have developed conceptual approaches to the assessment of innovation and investment, business methodology, competitiveness, financing of innovation, innovative

entrepreneurship and implementation of innovation policy enterprises in conditions of risk uncertainty. They also formulated strategic priorities for the development of the innovative economy in the Republic Uzbekistan for the long term in accordance with globalization, the long-term goals of socio-economic development of our country.

Research methodology

The research was conducted using the methods of scientific cognition. In order to identify trends in the development of innovations in the country, a practical analysis of the targets of innovative development of the economy was carried out. By the method of abstraction, conclusions were obtained about the features of using innovations as an indicator of investment policy. The method of generalization reveals the trends characteristic of developing countries in the implementation and decision-making of investment policy, as well as new phenomena of the country's innovative development path. Statistical data were obtained from the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The theoretical and methodological basis of the research is the works of representatives of classical, neoclassical and institutional economic theories. Its information and empirical base was the materials of monographs, articles by modern domestic and foreign economists; results of scientific and practical conferences. In the course of the research, formal-logical, systematic, deductive, inductive and economic-statistical methods, comparisons and analogies that allow us to describe economic phenomena and their properties.

Analysis and results

Undoubtedly, the results of realization of anti-crisis programs of development, forecast of the features of post-crisis period need new reconsideration of economic measures of the countries, especially, the countries with transitive economy. Being the member of any regional community, the Central Asia countries have the possibility to correct foreign economic policy, trade and economic relations, to deepen and widen branch-wise specialization of its economies directed to the rational using of natural resources, to create common regional infrastructure – industrial, informational and communicational, transport and others, to resolve jointly the issues of security, ecologic and other regional problems. As a result, in the region comprehensively production partnership is developed; national economies of the countries and its successful integration in the world community are strengthened. Significant role in the resolution of the tasks for overcoming crisis and providing dynamically stable development of the economy are innovations and innovative activity, which can provide steady renewal of technical and technological production, adoption and production of new competitive products, effective entering of products and services to the world markets. This requires the reformation of all spheres of social life and, first of all, its innovative modernization. This implies that the satiety of innovative activity is the key condition of forming effective innovative economy [2,3,6,13,14,15,16]. Efficiency of innovative activity is rather determined by innovative infrastructure which is the basic component of innovative economy and innovative potential of society.

Formation of innovative economy is substantially depends on creation of effective mechanisms of management of practical realization of complex innovative projects. And this process is impossible without government support. Necessity of financial and legal

support of science and innovations, activation of innovative activity, transition into the new forms of resolving economic, ecological and social problems of the regions, typical for innovative economy, strongly requires to develop responsible policy for management and development of innovative activity in the region by local authorities, to activate interaction between corporative business and local authorities on given issue. The main form of such interaction, on our opinion, should be through scientific and technical programs such as state programs of financing from budget, when important national economic issues are resolved on the basis of scientific innovative potential of regions with shared sponsorship of regional and state authorities.

Integrative processes and the experience of innovative way of development of developing countries can be rather applied to the countries of Central Asia region. Close cooperation of Central Asian countries in the framework of SCO, CIS and other foundations helps realization of over-mentioned tasks and directions. As an example, at present SCO serves common specified interests more widely than Central Asia region and opens new prospects of integrative relations with participation of leading countries that completely satisfy requirements of globalization and regionalism in the economic relations of Central Asia countries. The cooperation of the countries of the region is predetermined by the history and dictates the necessity of deepening the integrative relations [17,19,20,21]. The objective of innovative policy perfection during transaction to market relations and economic and financial stability of each country of Central Asian region is the important condition for development of integrative relations and for enhancement of national economies.

Participation of the country in realization of own model of economic development allows Uzbekistan for the short period of time to achieve essential successes in all key spheres and branches. For last two years the volume of implemented foreign investments increased more than 2,5 times. During the independence unit weight of industry in GDP increased more than 2,0 times, that testifies the forthcoming to the structure characterized for industrial countries. At the same time distinctive feature of structural changes in the industry of Uzbekistan is outrunning growth in the branches with highly technological level of industry, creating big added cost and increasing competitiveness of the country in comparison with development of traditional raw branches. Such branches as chemical, petrochemical industry and etc. continue to make major contribution to the development of industry.

Positive results significantly are achieved due to stimulation of production of finished and localized products, intensive technological modernization of enterprises in such branches as information and communication technology, gas-and-oil industry, nonferrous- and ferrous metals, chemical, pharmaceutical, light, ginning, fat-and-oil and construction material production industries. This process is related to transformation from production of raw industry to finished products with high share of added cost.

Today's changes in the international financial sphere and the last global financial-economic crisis itself dictate the necessity of constant renewal and modernization of production, and require concentration of all forces and resources of the country. Development of the Program for implementation of the most important priority projects aimed at modernization, technical and technological renewal and radical enhancement of

competitiveness and rise of export potential of economy including about 690 investment projects in fuel and energy, chemical, oil and gas processing, metallurgy sectors, light and textile industry, industry of construction materials and mechanical engineering, and other sectors of economy [24-30].

Conclusion

For successful realization of territorial innovative policy on forming innovative economy the complex of scientific and organizational measures should be implemented, the key from which are the following:

- development of conception of developing innovative activity and innovative infrastructure at the territory with determination of long-term strategic aims and facilities for its achievement within the framework of forming innovative economy;
- the program of innovative development of the region, which should be addressed indicating resources, executors, the period, and totality of measures directed to the achievement of aims of innovative development of the territory;
- organization of practical activity of the local authorities on realization and enactment of appropriate regulations on territorial level as well as organizational and informational provision of given program.

Researching the issues on innovative development of countries and on modernization of national economy we can make the following conclusions:

1. Industrial innovative development of national economies of countries is implemented through applying the system of innovative reforms in the country and through government support.
2. Applying of effective applied scientific-technical, engineering and technological development into the real sector of the economy, including modernization of the branches, technical and technological renewal, leads to the further development of national economies.
3. Wide development of banking system, active participation of international banks and other international financial institutes in economic reforms of Central Asian countries stimulates the development of industrial forces of the region, enhancement of foreign economic relations and strengthening of national economies of countries.

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6880920>

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